

MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN A FAST-GROWING UNIVERSITY TOWN OF OKITIPUPA, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA : CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

Samuel O. OLADAPO^{1*}, Olusola A. AKINTUNLAJI¹, Ajayi J. OLORUNTADE²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural and Bioresources Engineering, Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: so.oladapo@oaustech.edu.ng

Abstract

Increasing population because of the presence of a fast-growing university, amongst other factors, necessitates rising levels of municipal solid waste generation and the concerns for its management in Okitipupa. Therefore, the present study assessed the prevailing Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) techniques, challenges and prospects. Literature review, oral interviews and field surveys through visits to different waste dumpsites in the town, including on-site municipal solid waste analysis, were carried out to obtain information relating to relevant issues of concern. Findings show that food waste (25%) dominates the waste generated in the town, while metal (15%), paper (12.5%), plastic (10%) and others follow, in that order. In the absence of waste collection bins, trolleys, trucks, designated landfills and functional incinerators, open burning, dumping of waste on roadsides and abandoned/ undeveloped plots, drainage and river channels became the popular MSWM techniques adopted by many households in the town. Despite the challenges, opportunities for improved conditions are possible if all stakeholders, especially engineers develop the right facilities and equipment necessary to ensure good practices, including waste conversion to fertilizer and energy. Consequently, it was concluded that the lack of appropriate policy framework for waste management and non-enforcement of rules and regulations regarding urban planning led to unwholesome MSWM practices that are inimical to the environment in the area. Hence, the study recommended creation of an appropriate framework for MSWM by both public and private agencies, construction of engineered landfills at strategic locations to minimize waste dumping on inappropriate land surfaces, adoption of pay-as-you-generate policy, amongst others.

Keywords
municipal solid
waste,
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1. INTRODUCTION

All solid waste produced by a community's residential, commercial, and industrial sectors in a municipality is commonly referred to as municipal solid waste (MSW). Currently, increasing population has led to rising challenges of solid waste management in many cities across the world [1]. This is especially so in Okitipupa where population expansion has been witnessed following the establishment of Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology (OAUSTECH) since 2007 in the town. The rate, volume, and quality of MSW output have significantly increased in emerging nations due to population growth, fast urbanisation, a thriving economy, and rising living standards [2]. Globally, due to the rising volume of MSW generation, many communities, particularly in developing world, have encountered a concomitant increase in the challenges of municipal solid waste management (MSWM), with its potential negative effects on the environment [3-4]. This is especially true in many towns and cities in Nigeria, including Okitipupa, where large amounts of MSW are carelessly dumped into the environment due to the absence of a well-organised waste management system. Meanwhile, studies have shown a high correlation between effective waste management on one hand and environmental quality and healthy living on the other hand [5]. Thus, an understanding of the prevailing MSWM strategies may be of immense benefit to all stakeholders living in a fast-growing university town such as Okitipupa.

In any environment where humans live, waste is bound to be generated and thus should be managed. This is very important as inadequate MSWM at any community level has a negative influence on both human health and the ecosystem. For instance, air pollution from toxic gas emissions, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, volatile organic

compounds, particulate matter, etc., as well as soil and water contamination from leachates, are caused by open dumping, burning, or inappropriate landfilling. In addition to causing respiratory and neurological disorders, exposure to toxic gases has detrimental impacts on one's physical and emotional well-being [6]. Leachate mixing can contaminate fresh water, rendering it unusable by humans and uninhabitable by aquatic life [7]. Additionally, MSW management contributes to resource depletion, ocean pollution, and climate change on a worldwide scale [8]. Recent surveys and research show that, MSW accounts for between 3 and 5% of global anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [8-9]. Methane (CH₄) emissions from organic waste decomposition in landfills and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from waste burning are the primary sources of direct GHG emissions, whereas fossil fuel-based energy consumption and ineffective material recycling are the main causes of indirect emissions and resource depletion [10-11].

In many urban and peri-urban centres of Nigeria including Okitipupa, a well-defined regulation or laws guiding MSWM is rarely enforced, where they exist. This is because experience has shown that, in many instances, the enforcers of the law are also the real culprits. For example, the government whose responsibility is to provide the framework for MSWM, has hardly ever lived up to this expectation. Hence, different unwholesome methods of waste management techniques have been adopted in many municipalities in the country. Such methods include waste deposition on drainage channels, in-situ burning, street littering, dumping on bush and river, amongst others [12-13]. While deposition of waste on land surface and bushes constitutes unsightly scenes and creates breeding surfaces for pathogenic organisms; waste burial in pits and dumping in rivers lead to pollution of groundwater and surface water, respectively. In addition, open burning of waste emits air pollutants with its attendant health challenges.

As a regional headquarters for the people of Ondo South Senatorial District comprising Ikale, Ilaje, Apoi, Ijaw and many other tribes, Okitipupa has enjoyed rapid population expansion and urbanization since time immemorial. This has further been boosted by the increasing government presence since the return to civilian rule in 1999 and the establishment of OAUSTECH. Although the presence of the university initially appeared not to have added much due to the initial take-off problem of the institution, the recent surge in the number of faculties and courses (from three faculties to seven and with about 16 programmes added) run by the University have led to increasing students' enrolment. This has also given rise to increased quantity of MSW generated and further the challenges of waste disposal and management in the town. As well-defined techniques and procedures for MSW disposal and management are currently lacking, residents have chosen any methods that suit their purpose. Unfortunately, despite the several studies on MSWM in other parts of the country [14-16], except for Adeyemo and Demehin (2024), literature is sparse with respect to such studies in Okitipupa. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to assess MSWM strategies in a fast-growing university town of Okitipupa, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. The Study Area

The study area is Okitipupa, the headquarters of Okitipupa Local Government Area, Ondo State, Nigeria (Fig. 1). The town is located between latitudes 6° 30' 8.93" N and longitudes 4° 46' 46.25" E. With an area of about 803 km², its population based on the 2006 census figure was 233,565 residents [17]. Okitipupa is situated in the southern part of Ondo State, approximately 65 kilometers southeast of the state capital, Akure. It is bordered by Irele Local Government Area to the west and Odigbo Local Government Area to the east. Okitipupa is primarily an agrarian community, with farming being a major economic activity. Due to the abundance of basic facilities, Okitipupa has long served as the hub for residents of the Ondo South Senatorial District, comprising the local governments of Okitipupa, Irele, Ilaje, Ese Odo, Odigbo, and Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo. Given its well-drained, but fertile soil with abundance of rainfall, the mainstay of the people of the town is farming involving the cultivation of crops such as oil palm, cocoa, yam, cassava and maize, and fishery. Although Okitipupa faced the challenges of lack of power supply, because of disconnection from the national grid for more than ten years until year 2024, commercial activities have persistently been on the rise, especially with the advent of OAUSTECH in the town.

Fig. 1: Location of Okitipupa in Ondo State, Nigeria

2.2 Data Collection

The following methods were used to collect the data used for the present study: (i) desk study, involving gathering published information on municipal solid waste management in Okitipupa, from online journal articles and hardcopy prints, (ii) oral interviews of randomly selected households were conducted to extract information on the MSWM techniques adopted and their challenges, and (iii) field surveys, which entailed several visits to selected places for visual inspection and random on-site MSW analysis were carried out. Places visited include Ayeka, Igbodigo, Igodan, Okitipupa Main Market, Barack Road, New Garage Area, Idepe, Erinje Road, OAUSTECH (Mega and Permanent Campuses), amongst others.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Sources and Composition of Municipal Solid Waste in Okitipupa

Efficient MSWM can hardly be achieved without identifying the source, quantity and make-up of municipal solid waste, since they are the critical factors in determining how best to handle and manage the various wastes [2]. Information obtained from published sources showed that, until the first decade of the present century, Okitipupa like many other similar towns in Ondo State, was predominantly agrarian. However, many of the people especially women are into other different businesses, including hotel and tourism, restaurant, oil palm processing, selling of fish and its products, household needs such as groceries from which wastes are daily generated. But, with the coming of OAUSTECH, the tempo of activities has changed with the growing students' population, which requires additional need for privately-owned hostel accommodation and residential buildings for students and staff. The fact that the University currently does not have hostels and residential quarters for students and staff members, respectively, necessitates that they all must find abodes outside the campus. This also causes an increasing generation of paper waste, especially from business centres where typing, photocopies and other secretariat jobs are regularly done. According to a study by [15], the rise in population in Akure caused a sharp rise in social, commercial, and building activity, causing the transformation of MSW that was formerly composed of agricultural waste, to include industrial waste, plastics, paper, glass and wood.

Generally, notable differences usually exist in the composition of MSW across municipalities and between nations. In Okitipupa, increasing residential and hostel constructions have led to rising MSW from the sector in the form of rubble and other allied waste, based on field surveys and on-site waste analysis. This is because, in order to close the gap between population increase and housing needs, some smart landlords and private investors have had to acquire old and abandoned structures which are being modified to suit modern accommodation requirements. Moreover, because the students and staff come from different backgrounds and cultures with diverse tastes and consumption, there are changes in the varieties of solid waste generated. In this regard, domestic waste which was hitherto dominated by food waste has been diversified with the presence of foil papers, nylon bags and other packaging materials, given the presence of more fast-food business outlets where students and staff buy their food in takeaway containers. Meanwhile, a recent study reported that the structure of MSW in the town has considerably varied, with the composition of food waste ranging from 19.50% to 39.40%, depending on the area [18] (Table 1). Furthermore, while an earlier study observed a food waste composition of between 34.3% and 48.6% in Akure [15], a similar work in Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria, reported an average food waste percentage of about 26% across the different parts of the city [19]. Despite the foregoing report, huge sights of heaps of empty palm fruit bunches are also commonly found at the various oil palm processing plants located in the nooks and crannies of Okitipupa (Plate 1).

Table 1: Quantification of MSW in location sites across Okitipupa LGA

Parameters (%)	Okitipupa	Igodan	Okumo	OAUSTECH	Ayeka	Sabo	Ikoya	Erinje	Idepe	Igbodigo
Paper	12.50	21.40	18.30	20.50	17.50	33.20	16.80	16.30	38.30	37.40
Plastic	10.20	9.70	8.10	7.50	6.40	7.20	8.30	6.70	9.60	11.30
Metal	15.40	4.10	4.70	15.10	5.30	5.70	15.20	27.40	6.30	4.70
Food Wastes	25.20	39.40	36.50	31.50	29.30	38.40	27.50	28.20	24.70	19.50
Glass	12.40	4.50	7.40	5.70	18.40	3.30	18.50	7.70	9.40	10.20
Polythene Bags	2.70	1.40	3.50	5.20	1.70	1.60	2.00	1.80	3.40	0.90
Wood	7.40	3.70	7.80	4.10	3.00	2.30	1.90	2.00	1.80	2.80
Textile	6.70	7.50	7.50	1.70	11.90	2.10	1.50	1.90	4.70	10.20
Others	7.50	8.30	6.20	8.70	6.50	6.20	8.30	8.00	1.80	3.00
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: [18]

Plate 1: Empty palm fruit bunches at a location in Okitipupa

3.2 Prevailing MSWM Strategies in Okitipupa

The results of field surveys revealed that substantial amounts of MSW currently remain uncollected, and waste disposal in the town is still mostly haphazard and unregulated. Though a privately run MSW collection services exists in the town [18], majority of the dwellers do not embrace it because they are hesitant to pay. Besides, results of oral interviews with the locals showed that the handling of waste by the private organisations was perceived inadequate as they lack proper treatment or dumping practices for the collected waste. Respondents also added that burning trash in open landfills was the prevalent MSW treatment technique by the collectors. Consequently, the practice has been widely embraced by most of the households in the town. Field surveys further showed that most households have created a small portion within their compounds where solid waste (refuse) is daily dumped, allowed to dry and thereafter openly burnt. This practice, though pollutes the air, has been reported in many previous studies as very rampant in most developing countries, including Nigeria [16,19,20,21].

Another common MSWM practice amongst the inhabitants is open dumping on roadsides, especially on bushes and abandoned/uncompleted plots (Plate. 2). With respect to this, certain lands consecrated for cultural celebrations are also not exempted from the unwholesome practice. Meanwhile, it was earlier reported that due to the inability of the residents of Okitipupa to pay for waste collection, majority of the locals chose to dump their waste in any open place, indiscriminately [18]. Scholars in Sub-Saharan Africa and other parts of the world have also reported a similar pattern [22-24]. However, the method is condemnable, because it constitutes nuisance in the environment and creates breeding sites for all kinds of pathogenic and parasitic organisms, including mosquitoes and rodents [8]. In addition, indiscriminate dumping of waste on land surfaces creates opportunities for in-situ decay and thereby leads to emissions of carbon dioxide and methane gases which are both GHG exacerbating anthropogenic climate change [20,25].

In OAUSTECH where field surveys and on-site MSW analysis have shown that considerable quantities of nylon, paper and plastic waste are generated daily, there is no evidence also to show that the University handles the waste better. For example, at the Mega Campus where the School of Engineering is situated, the only incinerator constructed to serve the campus is currently an abandoned facility with no slight hope of its operation soon. For

this reason, solid wastes comprising predominantly paper and plastic containers collected by the campus cleaners, are daily heaped somewhere within the premises (Plate 3). From field surveys and oral interviews, the ultimate treatment for the heap of waste has always been open burning which is done at no specific intervals. Unfortunately, the situation at the permanent site of the university campus appeared not better off, as there was no visible standard method for MSWM put in place.

Plate 2: MSW on roadsides in Okitipupa

Plate 3: Waste dumped in School of Engineering premises, OAUSTECH

Similarly, field surveys also indicated that dumping MSW along drainage and river channels is also a common practice amongst the people (Plate 4). This is commonly done with the belief that the waste will be washed away once it rains. In many developing countries, due to lack of suitable landfills and efficient MSW collection systems, massive volumes of solid and garbage debris are being dumped into open canals and drains, thereby obstructing

them [2]. This technique is unsuitable as it causes erosion and flash floods, due to its detrimental effects on free flow of runoff along drainage channels. Furthermore, the waste deposited may finally find its way into different water bodies, thereby causing enrichment or eutrophication with grave negative effects on aquatic lives.

Plate 4: MSW dumped along a drainage channel

3.3 Challenges of MSWM in Okitipupa

Since the best and most suitable waste collection and disposal methods are not being used, MSWM conditions in Okitipupa can be described as precarious and in a dire need of attention. In the first instance, our field surveys and oral interviews showed that a publicly owned, well-organised and properly funded waste collection and management agency does not exist, currently in the town. This is in contrast with the situation in the past, specifically during the first and a half decade of the present millennium, when the state government gladly funded the distribution of waste bins, trolleys and conveyance trucks across cities and urban towns [15]. Obviously, the present scenario makes MSW collection from different households, transportation and deposition at the designated landfills virtually impossible, despite the expansion of the town. Linked to the foregoing is the absence of an institutional framework for MSWM in the town. This is evident in the fact that the inhabitants are allowed to handle their waste as they like, since there is no indication that perpetrators of such unwholesome practices are being held responsible for their actions. Moreover, it is doubtful if appropriate urban planning and waste management laws are being implemented in the town, which could have helped to reduce abandoned land spaces that currently serve as waste dumps. [20] had earlier noted that enforcement of rules and bylaws, such as making sure private operators utilise suitable covered vehicles for waste collection and transportation to disposal locations, is critical for efficient MSWM.

In addition, there is no evidence of deliberate attempt by the inhabitants to separate waste to enhance ease of handling. Sorting and separation prior to collection lowers the total cost of MSW disposal, facilitates material recycling, and decreases the amount of solid waste generated [1]. This is because doing so can help in resource recovery and reuse, while also creating opportunities for waste conversion to wealth. Furthermore, waste separation also helps handlers to take decisions on the procedures for final disposal. However, since discarding waste as they are generated is more convenient, households do not bother to sort and separate. Close to this, there is the problem of non-recycling of waste by households. This is probably because, recycling process is tasking, consequent upon the fact that waste is rarely separated and there are no incentives to encourage scavengers to carry out the procedure.

The absence of well-constructed and properly managed engineered sanitary landfills around Okitipupa also constitutes a critical challenge to MSWM in the town. Globally, substantial amounts of MSW in most developing

countries are landfilled, nonetheless, available landfills in the town are mere open dumps which do not conform to any engineering requirement and, as such, dangerous to the environment [26]. This is because, away from the fact that the biological breakdown of organic matter produces biogas, which is a major problem in landfills and is mainly made up of methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), the leachate from open dumps also causes both surface and groundwater contamination, that is inimical to the health of both terrestrial and aquatic lives.

Added to the foregoing is the problem of non-availability of functional incinerators in the town. Waste incineration, which is the process of burning solid waste at high temperatures to reduce its volume and mass, and sometimes to recover energy, usually provides opportunities to convert waste to wealth. Unfortunately, as earlier mentioned, the only known one within the premises of the Mega Campus of OAUSTECH is currently inoperative. Even at that, due to the high concentration of food waste and the moisture content of the waste generated in the town, leading to poor calorific value, it may be far too low for waste heat utilisation and unsuitable for incineration.

3.4 Prospects of a Better Tomorrow in MSWM in Okitipupa

Despite the aforementioned challenges, there is hope for a better future regarding MSWM in the town. First, for the appropriate management of the prevailing unofficial system, authorities at the local levels need to think about re-structuring and overseeing it. When this is done, it can serve the twin purpose of ensuring effectiveness in the collection of MSW with job creation, and at the same time revenue generation for the government. Through this way, scavengers can be encouraged to supply enough cheap labour to truly implement recycling procedures in place of the local government.

Lack of waste collection bins and trolleys also presents an opportunity for engineers to design and fabricate suitable ones for use in the locality. Through this, the engineers involved and OAUSTECH stand to benefit financially from the mass production of such equipment, especially if backed by an appropriate government policy. Also, given that a major hinderance to waste separation and recycling is the lack of machines that could help in sorting [2], overcoming this challenge may require the service of engineers. This will also necessitate the development of suitable machines, which can be undertaken with appropriate grants. Such machines when finally produced, can be patented to become an intellectual property of the inventors and, at the same time boost the image of the University.

Waste conversion to fertilizer is an area that may be considered for substantial opportunities for scientists and engineers. This is possible given that the greater component of the MSW in Okitipupa is made of food waste and other organic materials that are biodegradable. In places where wastes with high organic content are produced, it is often advisable to use anaerobic digestion units to produce biogas or fertilizer from the primary component [26]. This is also very beneficial from a bioeconomic standpoint, since 30% of non-renewable energy is recycled, and waste generation from biofertilization and commercialisation is a suitable method of recovering nutrients from waste [27].

Other areas of opportunity may include waste conversion to energy which has received wide acceptance amongst many countries in Asia and Africa, recently [8]. Moreover, the creation of drop-off centres can also provide opportunities for waste recovery, while also creating an avenue for financial benefits for households.

4. CONCLUSION

The study investigated the prevailing MSWM strategies, the challenges and prospects in a fast-growing university town of Okitipupa. Thus, we found obvious reasons to conclude that the existing system is unwholesome and not operated under any legal framework. Besides, there are also reasons to believe that urban planning rules and regulations on waste management are presently being poorly enforced, if they ever exist. Accordingly, households and organisations adopt waste management techniques that suit their purpose, without minding whether they are environmentally friendly or not. Our findings show that the commonest and most popular waste management techniques amongst the inhabitants are open burning, dumping on land surfaces, roadsides, and drainage and river channels. Unfortunately, the use of modern technologies such as engineered landfills, incineration, waste separation and recycling, conversion to biogas and fertilizers and biodiesel production, are not available for the households to embrace. Adoption of the foregoing techniques can confer some economic benefits to people in the area and elsewhere considering the large quantities of organic waste being generated. Consequently, the following recommendations are found useful:

i. there is a need for municipal institutions to regulate the unofficial system, by creating an appropriate framework for MSWM by both public and private agencies.

- ii. establishment of engineered landfills at strategic locations around the town will help minimize the resort to self-help through waste dumping on inappropriate land surfaces.
- iii. residential solid waste output is currently unrestricted, and the ease of waste disposal encourages increasing solid waste production, thus, adoption of pay-as-you-generate policy may be a good strategy.
- iv. there should be a deliberate attempt by scientists and engineers in the universities to conduct adequate research with a view to engendering appropriate solutions for MSWM in the environment.
- v. adoption of integrated municipal waste management (IMWM) techniques which usually stem from the separation of the recyclables and organic waste with high moisture, will also help to overcome the challenge of the high quantity of waste that needs to be disposed of.
- vi. given that many households cannot appreciate the danger involved in unwholesome MSWM practices, there may be the need for public education and awareness campaigns.

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